

Open Education as a Public Good: From Lock-in to Democratic Infrastructure

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May 2026

ABSTRACT

This paper analyses the current conjuncture of digital education across three levels: (1) a landscape shaped by the confluence of right-wing authoritarianism and Big Tech ideology; (2) a regime shaped by proprietary platforms and vendor lock-in; and (3) a niche of open-source and OER communities working to build democratic alternatives. I argue that the transition towards Open Education as a Digital Public Good is not primarily a technical challenge but foremost a democratic one, requiring landscape critique, infrastructural policy, and institutional recognition of care work.

1. "BUILDING BETTER DIGITAL EDUCATION" – BUT WHAT DO WE TAKE FOR GRANTED?

For over a decade, education has been framed as part of a “digital transformation”, in which “(...) it is routinely claimed that the educational institutions that produce and circulate knowledge are being (or will soon be) augmented through advances in digital technologies, data and artificial intelligence (AI), which are reshaping how knowledge is made and circulated” (Williamson et al., 2025, S. 936). Therefore, digital infrastructures become a significant factor, especially when they are commercially provided, and can lead to “digital democratic deficits” (e.g., erosion of pedagogic autonomy). Although digital sovereignty is now all over the political agenda, it is often constrained to competitiveness and with little commitment to the public good and to democratic control (cf. Pohle, 2023). Against this background, Open Education seems to offer some solutions to these predicaments, which are subsumed under the umbrella term “Digital Public Good” (UNESCO, 2024). However, openness is not a straightforward concept in the sense of “the more, the better” and in order to aim for “better digital education”, careful consideration is advised.

It is therefore only logical to demand that digital infrastructures should be open and shaped not just by engineers and designers, but by the public. Nevertheless, this short paper argues that we should first take a step back and raise some fundamental questions about "digital education":

- Who decides what "better" education looks like – and on whose terms?
- Whose values are encoded in the tools we use every day?
- When we talk about "digital education", do we mean education shaped by technology – or technology shaped by educational values?

Those questions are meant to address the tendency to conflate the promises made by technology companies with the realities of educational practice. Critical scholar Neil Selwyn describes this as the "orthodoxy of educational technology":

"(...) educational technology tends to be promoted and publicized by actors from all sides of the 'education community' as a natural, necessary and largely neutral element of contemporary education. (...) digital technologies are an integral and inevitable feature of 'modern' forms of education, and therefore require little or no discussion."
(Selwyn, 2014, p. 2)

This orthodoxy has prevented a critical analysis of the claims attached to digital technologies used in schools and universities. In many recent discussions related to the impact of AI, it is framed as having “transformative potential” for teaching, research and administration, i.e. it is a given, natural force and educational institutions must adapt to that.

It has also made education vulnerable to a techno-authoritarian take-over (Costello & Gow, 2025).

2. MAKING SENSE OF THE MESS: A MULTI-LEVEL PERSPECTIVE

How can we deal with a situation in which the future of education and of society at large seems to be predetermined by Silicon Valley? To unpack current discourses, this paper proposes a multi-level perspective (MLP). This approach was originally developed by Geels (2002) to account for technological transitions, such as those from sailing ships to steamships between 1780 and 1900. The MLP distinguishes three levels, each with distinctive logics, rules and principles: landscape, regime, and niche.

The model has proven to be valuable for explaining (resisting) change in domains such as the greening of industry (Penna & Geels, 2012) or digital education (Deimann & Lukács, 2026).

In the following discussion, the three levels of the MLP will be applied to the context of digital education.

Landscape: Ideological Pressure from Above

The landscape represents broader structural trends and discourses, including global policy agendas. As became visible in January 2025 during the inauguration of Donald Trump in Washington, tech moguls such as Jeff Bezos, Mark Zuckerberg and Elon Musk sat centre stage and replaced elected politicians. Later that same day, Elon Musk made a salute widely interpreted as

a fascist gesture (Coeckelbergh, 2026). For many observers, this was surprising because for quite a long time, Silicon Valley had appeared aligned with the values of liberal democracy. However, as Becca Lewis (2025) has detailed, there are much darker ideological roots beneath the surface.

The most striking illustration is Marc Andreessen's so-called Techno-Optimist Manifesto (2023). This text argues that technological progress is not merely beneficial but a moral imperative. Regulation, democratic oversight, and institutional caution are framed as obstacles to human flourishing. The state must not interfere. Society must not slow down. Progress, by definition, cannot be wrong.

This is not the eccentric opinion of one investor. It reflects a broader ideological pattern that the scholar David Golumbia (2024) has described as a *pipeline*: a set of assumptions and values that originate in Silicon Valley and flow, largely unexamined, into institutions, including universities. The pipeline operates through the language of "innovation" and "disruption", which sound neutral or even progressive, but carry a specific set of commitments: market logic over public good, speed over deliberation, technological solutions over educational ones.

This matters for education because when digital tools are adopted uncritically, it is not just software that is being adopted. The values inscribed in that software come with it. Elon Musk's self-described "anti-woke" AI chatbot Grok is the most visible example, yet the pipeline runs much deeper and much more quietly than that. Therefore, it is not sufficient to work towards open infrastructure in education. Equally important is the simultaneous work of debunking ideologies such as those included in the TESCREAL bundle (Gebu & Torres, 2024) and replacing them with values rooted in educational principles: participation, autonomy, and critical thinking.

Regime: Lock-in as the Default

The regime comprises institutions, infrastructures, and norms that stabilise current educational and technological systems. In digital education, the regime is shaped by a fundamental tension: on one side, a growing body of open policies and initiatives; on the other, the structural dominance of proprietary platforms.

Consider learning management systems: Across many European universities, platforms such as Canvas, Blackboard, or Microsoft Teams have become the default infrastructure for teaching and learning. They are deeply embedded in IT contracts, staff workflows, and student expectations. Switching is costly, technically complex, and institutionally risky. When a university's pedagogical practice is organised around a proprietary platform, the platform begins to define what teaching looks like, what counts as participation, and what data gets collected.

Against this backdrop, OER policies represent an important countermovement within the regime. Over the last years, many such policies have been published on a global scale, documented in the OER Policy Registry (Havemann et al.,

2020). They encourage teachers and academic staff to produce, use and distribute openly licensed materials, with support through personnel, training and infrastructure. The goal is to make open-source tools and OER the new normal in daily practice.

But policies alone are not sufficient to shift the regime. As long as proprietary platforms remain the dominant infrastructure, open content and Open Source projects risk being absorbed into closed environments. The scale of this dependency in the German context remains empirically underexplored. This is a gap that the ongoing project on “Digital independence and resilience of higher education institutions in teaching and learning” is currently addressing through a systematic survey of software use, costs and structural dependencies at German universities (Gesellschaft für Informatik, 2026).

Niche: Open Education as an Alternative

The niche is where alternatives are born, tested and refined, often by small communities working outside the mainstream, with limited resources but strong convictions. In the context of digital education, the niche is populated by open-source developers, OER communities, and educators who have long insisted that another digital education is possible.

A compelling example is Public AI, a non-profit, open-source initiative that provides access to AI tools and models while prioritising transparency, community control, and educational purposes (Sieker et al., 2025). Unlike commercial AI systems, Public AI is not optimised for profit or data extraction. This is precisely what a niche innovation looks like: it challenges the logic of the dominant regime not by competing on its own terms, but by demonstrating that different terms are possible.

However, niche innovations face a structural challenge. They depend on care work, i.e., the largely invisible but crucial labour of maintaining infrastructures, writing documentation, organising events like hackathons and OER sprints, and keeping knowledge commons alive. This work is rarely funded, rarely recognised, and rarely counted in the metrics that institutions use to measure value. A promising example of institutional recognition is the Open Source Development Network (OSDN), based in Lower Saxony, Germany, which explicitly funds and coordinates open-source development in higher education, demonstrating that care work can become a matter of public policy (Hochschule.digital Niedersachsen, 2026).

As outlined by Geels and Schot (2007), niches must build sufficient internal momentum through learning processes and institutional support for a regime change. In the context of Open Education, there are reasons for cautious optimism with Open Source projects for teaching and learning. Nevertheless, as indicated by the preceding landscape analysis, the ideological pressure is having a counterproductive effect on the niche's development.

3. CONCLUSION: RECLAIMING THE UTOPIA

Taken together, the multi-level perspective reveals that the transition towards an open-source ecosystem in education is not primarily a technical challenge, it is foremost a democratic one. Three conclusions follow, one for each level.

At the landscape level, we need to name what is happening. The confluence of right-wing authoritarianism and Big Tech is not an accident, and it is not temporary. It is the visible expression of a pipeline of ideological assumptions flowing into educational institutions through the language of innovation, disruption and inevitability. Naming this pipeline is not pessimism but a precondition for changing it. We need alternative narratives rooted in educational values: solidarity, care, and community. We need to reclaim the terms "innovation" and "disruption" for democratic purposes.

At the regime level, we need to translate open policies into open infrastructure. Policies are necessary but not sufficient. As long as proprietary platforms remain the default, open content risks being absorbed into closed systems. The concept of the Digital Public Good (open code, open standards, open policies) offers orientation for what a democratic digital infrastructure could look like. This is not utopian; it is already happening, in projects, in institutions that have chosen a different path.

At the niche level, we need to invest in the communities doing the work. This means funding care work, recognising open-source contribution as a form of scholarly and civic labour, and creating protected spaces for experimentation. Hackathons, OER sprints and networks such as OSDN are not marginal activities. They are the seedbed of the regime we want to build.

Open Education, at its best, is not just a set of tools. It is a practice of democracy.

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